

Purification of SLC31A1 from Expi293F™ Cells

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Authors	¹ David B. Sauer, ¹ Huanyu Li, ¹ Sagar Raturi, ¹ Andreea Scacioc, ¹ Tina Bohstedt, ¹ Abilasha Balakrishnan
Affiliations	¹ Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford. Oxford, UK

Protocol description

This protocol is used to purify the SLC transporter expressed in Expi293F™ Cells using detergent solubilization followed by a series of different chromatographic methods. Depending on the nature of the expression construct and experimental requirements, the GFP tag can be removed using a proteolytic reaction.

Materials

Biological materials:	
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HEPES (Apollo Scientific, catalog number BI8181)▪ NaCl (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number S9888)▪ 5-Cyclohexyl-1-Pentyl-β-D-Maltoside (CYMAL-5) (Anatrace, catalog number C325)▪ cOmplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche, catalog number 11873580001)▪ Imidazole (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number 56750)▪ Glycerol (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number G5516)▪ TALON® Metal Affinity Resin, (Takara Bio, catalog number 635653)▪ TEV (Tobacco Etch Virus) protease (produced in-house)▪ PD 10 Desalting Columns (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number GE17-0851-01)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Gravity flow columns▪ 50 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrators▪ 96 well block (2 mL)▪ WHEATON® Dounce Tissue Grinder, 40 mL (DWK Life Sciences, catalog number 357546)▪ AVESTIN - EMULSIFLEX-C3 (C3 homogeniser) (Wolflabs, catalog number EF-C3)

Reagents setup

- **Stock solution:** 10% (w/v) CYMAL-5 in Base buffer. Rotate at 4 °C overnight to allow complete solubilisation and store at -20 °C.
- Base buffer (50 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol)
- TALON wash buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 20 mM Imidazole, 0.24% CYMAL-5)
- TALON elution buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM Imidazole, 0.24% CYMAL-5)
- SEC buffer (20 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 0.15% CYMAL-5), filtered through 0.22 µm membrane

Procedure

▪ Part A of protocol / day 1

1. Thaw the frozen cell pellet in a water bath set to room temperature.
2. Add lysis buffer by adding 3 tablets of Protease Inhibitor Cocktail tablet to 150 mL of base buffer. Allow the tablets to dissolve.
3. Suspend thawed pellets with lysis buffer and pour into a Dounce homogeniser. Homogenise the solution by pulling and pushing the plunger up and down approximately 20 times. Keep on ice.

4. Break the cells by passing through a **C3** homogenizer at **10,000 psi** pressure 2 times. Keep on ice.
5. Add CYMAL-5 stock solution to the lysed cells to a final concentration of 1%.
4. Rotate the container slowly for 1 hour at 4 °C.
5. Centrifuge the solution at 50,000 x g for 30 min at 4 °C.
6. Equilibrate 4-6 mL bed volume of TALON resin with the base buffer.
7. Collect the supernatant and add equilibrated TALON resin to the supernatant, rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
8. Transfer the solution to a gravity flow column, allow the solution to flow through.
9. Wash the resin with 10 times the bed volume of TALON wash buffer.
10. Perform elution with 5 times the bed volume of TALON elution buffer.

PD-10 desalting

11. Pre-equilibrate PD-10 column with SEC buffer.
12. Add 2.5 mL of the eluted protein sample per PD-10 column. Spin the column at 1000 xg for 2 minutes. Collect the flow through.
13. Measure protein concentration using nanodrop. If the protein has a TEV cleavage site followed by a GFP tag (and if the GFP tag needs removal), add TEV protease to the protein solution in a 1:2.5 (w/w) TEV:protein ratio.
14. Slowly rotate the container overnight at 4 °C.

▪ **Part B of protocol / day 2**

15. In a gravity flow column, equilibrate 2-4 mL bed volume of TALON resin with SEC buffer.
16. Add equilibrated TALON resin to the overnight TEV reaction mixture and rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
17. Using an empty gravity flow column let the solution collect flow through solution in a 50 kDa cut-off centrifugal filter.
18. Concentrate the solution by centrifuging at 3,000 xg at 4 °C, stop and gently agitate every 5 minutes.
19. Equilibrate a Superose 6 Increase 10/300 GL column using SEC buffer.
20. Concentrate the sample down to the desired injection volume and inject the sample into the sample loop.
21. Run a SEC elution.
22. Pool peak fractions in a fresh 50 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrator and concentrate to the required volume/concentration at 3,000 xg at 4 °C.

Additional notes

1. The amount of solubilisation buffer depends on the cell pellet volume. We recommend using 30-40 mL solubilisation buffer per litre cell culture. The above protocol has been adapted for cell pellet from 4 L culture.
2. The TEV treatment step is to be carried out only if the GFP tag needs to be removed.

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.